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Elements of the Cultural Space as a Form Identity of Klungkung Urban Area, Bali, Indonesia

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Abstract

The identity of cities in Indonesia has a different character and spatial structure, especially in the Klungkung urban area, Bali. Identifying urban areas will be able to understand who, what, patterns, and needs that must be met. The identity of urban areas is based on the order and function of urban life that is integrated in the socio-cultural values of the city residents as the soul and identity of the city, as well as the physical elements of the city. In the urban environment there are cultural space elements as indicators and references for the development of the identity of the Klungkung urban area, Bali. This research is based on the low level of understanding and form of community implementation, and the government on city identity and lack of public awareness about culture as the holder of an important role as a form of urban identity. Space Culture, as a city identity in the development of urban areas, is increasingly lost and not directed. Identity originating from the Local Elements of Space Elements will affect all aspects of the development of elements forming the character of urban areas. There are several concepts of Balinese Space Elements that can provide a touch of identity for urban areas, namely the history of traditions and beliefs, a system of values, art and cultural space settings which include fixed, semi-fixed and non-fixed elements. This research uses qualitative methods by applying descriptive, hermeneutic, and literature studies. This study aims to find out what elements of cultural space become the identity form of Klungkung Urban Area, Bali. From the results of the analysis in the conceptual order, the benefits and results obtained are obtained to provide an overview of the local cultural space elements as the identity of the Klungkung urban area. Whereas in the operational order it can formulate policies regarding the identity of urban development. In the future, the results of this study are expected to be input in determining the shape and pattern of the identity of an urban area.

Keywords: Balinese Cultural Elements, Space Settings, Urban Identity, Urban Areas

INTRODUCTION

Background

Klungkung urban area is an area that has a long history and is a central area for the development of kingdoms in Bali. Local culture is inseparable from the identity of an urban area. The development of the Klungkung urban area has increasingly advanced, especially seen from the arrangement of cities and historic buildings

that have a high historical value. Klungkung urban area is divided into several regional functions, both commercial, historical, office, and service areas.

The identity of the Klungkung urban area is needed for the advancement of an area, currently, the Klungkung District Government is in the spirit of developing and improving various aspects of excellence in the potential of culture, tourism and the identity of the Klungkung urban area. Almost all regions in Klungkung Regency that have potential will be developed as cultural space identities and tourism attractiveness as a form of identity for urban development. The wisdom of local culture is also reflected in the concept of zoning, which views the mountain as an upstream zone or a head that is sacred or sacred. Bali captures space through Hindu cosmology. In this approach, the macro cosmos and human space are microcosms, both of which contain the same elemental value. The emphasis is on achieving harmony between the macrocosm and the microcosm.

Developing a city that is culturally-minded is one of the visions that have been discussed by all regions in Bali, then continued in the following period, the discourse of "ajeg Bali" emerged which was an effort towards sustainable development based on Balinese culture. This is so that the unique Balinese culture is maintained and preserved in accordance with the conditions that develop in the sense of accepting the movement of cultural change but still in the corridor of Balinese culture.

With a strong history and background of Klungkung, the central government of the Balinese kings in Klungkung has an important and very central role in the area of Bali, namely the very influential Role of Puri Klungkung from the Dutch colonial period to the kingdoms in the Bali region. Klungkung Regency has a very diverse potential of cultural customs, such as dances, small industries, paintings, and several temples and puri, which can be classified as cultural heritage. Puri is a history of the past that is full of meaning and full of dynamics of life in its heyday. Puri as the center of government, the center of culture, education, and socio-economic life of the people of the city of Klungkung. In the future, the Klungkung area can provide an overview of the elements of local cultural space as a form of identity for urban areas in Bali

Research Question

Based on the background stated above, the research questions faced by the Klungkung urban area are as follows:

1. How is the development of the Klungkung urban area seen from the history and local cultural space?
2. What elements of cultural space are the identities of the development of the Klungkung urban area?

Research Objectives

The choice of this research topic is focused on cultural elements that play a major role in developing a future urban area. From the position of this research, the author tries to connect the cultural linkages to the development of urban areas in Bali and has a purpose

- 1 Knowing how cultural space can give shape to the identity of an Urban Area
- 2 Knowing the contribution given by city identity to the development of urban areas
- 3 Knowing the strategy for developing an urban area based on culture as the identity of a city in Bali
- 4 City Identity Can contribute to the development of Urban areas

Outcome Targets and Research Benefits

This study emphasizes more on the elements of local cultural space as a form of identity for an urban area where the history of traditions, beliefs, values systems, arts, and cultural space settings include fixed, semi-fixed and non-fixed elements.

Besides that, this research is expected to be able to provide great benefits and contributions to the government and the community and as a future reference both at national and international levels about elements of cultural space as a form of urban identity which includes:

1. Providing an overview of elements of cultural space as a form of identity of an urban area throughout Indonesia
2. The importance of city identity in contributing to the development of urban areas in Indonesia
3. Providing a knowledge that City Identity Can make a major contribution to the development of Urban areas for Southeast Asian and Asian countries
4. Can provide a strategy for developing urban areas based on culture as urban identities in Southeast Asian and Asian countries

Literature Review

The noble values of Balinese culture, namely things that are considered good and valuable in the sustainability of community life and culture include a range of abstract elements (intangible culture, non-object cultural elements) consisting of: 1. Philosophical Element: It is the most basic and most abstract element, containing basic essence and truth. Value Element: It is a basic element of valuable things in life, generally as a collective representation. 3. Concept Elements It is an element that is more instrumental and closer to the implementation level. Elements of Norms and Rules It is an element related to daily real life and practical value.

In the context and order of Urban design, spatial can be interpreted as relating to space (Trancik). Space consists of hard space and soft space. The principle of hard space is that which is limited by architectural walls intended to accommodate social activities (Trancik). Soft space area which is dominated by natural environments, such as parks, gardens, or green lanes. From this, it is known that there is a relationship between architectural / building work and natural environment in forming space. From that understanding, it can be said that spatial is the relationship that occurs between buildings, cultural environment, and space in accommodating human activities.

Settings are the layout of an interaction between humans and their environment (Rapoport 1982). Settings cover the environment in which humans (communities) are located (land, water, space, air, trees, other living things). That is to know the place and situation with which they are related because different situations have different layouts. In the context of space, settings can be distinguished by physical settings and activities/activity settings. Based on its constituent elements, the settings can be distinguished on (Rapoport, 1982):

1. Fixed elements are elements that are basically fixed, or changes are rare. Spatially these elements can be organized into size, location, sequence, and arrangement. But in the case of a phenomenon, these elements can be complemented by other elements. Includes: building and road equipment attached.
2. The semi-fixed element is a rather fixed element but still ranges from the arrangement and type of elements, such as road elements, advertising signs, shop windows, and other urban elements. The changes are quite fast and easy. Includes: street vendors, parking and marker systems.
3. Non-fixed elements are elements that are related to behavior or behavior shown by humans themselves, which are always not fixed, such as body position and body posture and body movements. Includes: pedestrians, motorized, and non-motorized vehicle movements.

The city is not a built environment that was built in a short time but was formed in a long time and is an accumulation of each stage of previous development. As stated by Rossi (1982), that the city is a collective physical artifact and was built for a long time and through a process that is rooted in the culture of its people. Cities are basically able to create uniqueness or distinctive characteristics such as the center of business, culture, art, or science and technology (science and technology), which are processed based on prominent characters or identities that have been owned from the beginning. city identity is not in the sense of the similarity of an object to another, but rather refers to the meaning of individuality which reflects the difference between other objects and their recognition as separate entities "(Lynch, 1960)

City identity is a mental image that is formed from the biological rhythms of certain places and spaces that reflect time (sense of time), which are grown from within rooted in the socio-economic activities of the city society itself (Lynch, 1972). Understanding is said that identity is a condition when someone is able to recognize or recall (memory) a place that has a difference with another place because it has character and uniqueness. Identity is a very important fundamental thing. When compared to these two forms of identity, it is likely that psychic identity is a form of identity that is actually more realistic and applicable to be considered and put forward as a city identity discourse because it is more rooted in the cultural values, functions and life order of the community, without having to ignore the physical conditions cities in an integrated and complementary manner.

There are 3 components that greatly affect the mental picture or image of people towards an area (Kevin Lynch 1969), namely:

1. Identity; Cities have the potential to be "read," meaning that people will understand the urban image (identification of objects, differences between objects, things that can be known).
2. Structure; City has the potential to. 'Compiled' means that people can experience urban space (the relation of objects, object-subject relations, visible patterns).
3. Meaning; Cities have the potential to "imagine" meaning that people can experience urban space (meaning objects, meaning subject-objects, feelings that can be experienced) is an understanding of meaning by observers of two components (identity and structure of cities) through dimensions: symbolic, functional, emotional historical, cultural, political and spatial planning. City imagery is formed from several elements, according to Kevin Lynch, namely: Landmarks, edges, pathways, nodes, and districts.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research emphasizes qualitative methods by applying a descriptive approach. Where in this study explained, identifying elements of Balinese cultural space using qualitative methods, and literature studies. Data collection techniques are carried out by direct observation to the field, interviews, and literature studies relating to elements of Balinese cultural space. This study aims to find out how the development of urban areas in Klungkung is seen from spatial elements and activities of Balinese culture. This research was conducted to find new elements of local Balinese culture that can be used as guidelines in giving meaning to the identity of urban areas in major cities in Indonesia in particular and cities of the world in general.

Stages of Data Collection

1. Primary data is obtained directly from the field through observation and through interviews with informants. The primary data collection method was carried out by direct interviews with the Klungkung community, Klungkung cultural leaders, Klungkung district government and field documentation per place and per view of the City Area in Klungkung Regency
2. Secondary data, in the form of documents or literature from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), internet, newspapers, accredited journals, and so on. Secondary data collection is done by taking or using several / all data sets that have been recorded or reported and adapted to the field conditions that occur.

Data analysis and conclusions

1. Data analysis using descriptive analysis was conducted to identify people's understanding of the elements of cultural space as forming the identity of the Klungkung city area. Data analysis was carried out through three channels, namely data reduction, data presentation, withdrawal of the data reduction stage is the process of sorting samples considered to meet the criteria, including local indigenous culture and acculturation if fulfilling the criteria. Including and if not deleted.
2. Conclusion of research and recommendations: formulate conclusions and suggestions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results

Overview The research location of Klungkung Regency is the smallest Regency of 9 (Nine) Districts and Cities in the Province of Bali with an area of 315 km² geographically located between 115.21'28 " - 115.37'43 " East Longitude and 008.27o 37 o - 008.49o 00 o South Latitude. The boundaries of the Klungkung Regency are in the north bordering Bangli Regency, east of Karangasem Regency in the south of the Indian Ocean and in the west bordering Gianyar Regency.

Figure 1. The location of the study site in Southeast Asia

Source: Author Analysis 2019

The Klungkung regency is divided into 4 sub-districts, namely: Banjarangkan, Klungkung, Dawan and Nusa Penida. A third of the Klungkung Regency area (112.16 km²) is located between the island of Bali and two thirds (202.84 km²) are islands, namely Nusa Penida, Nusa Lembongan, and Nusa Ceningan. The focus of this study is to take the location in Klungkung Regency precisely in the Klungkung sub-district and focus on the Klungkung urban area

Figure 2. The focus of the research location is in the Klungkung urban area

Source: Author Analysis 2019

Based on Klungkung data In macro terms, the spatial structure of the Klungkung area is formed by the components of spatial structure and urban design elements. Each component of the spatial structure forms an interaction mechanism through the order of functional activities that support each other. The main area spatial components that play a role in the structure of the Klungkung Klungkung urban area include Core Areas. Spatial components included in the core zone are the Klungkung City Region. The Buffer Zone Zone. Spatial components included in the Gel-Gel Area. And the area off into the Banjarangkan and Dawan sub-districts.

The results of the analysis of elements of cultural space as a form of identity in the Klungkung urban area are:

History and tradition

If seen from its development from the time of the founding of the kingdom, resistance to colonialism, the transfer of the royal capital to the era of independence, the Klungkung area which is now the capital of samarapura has an important and very central role and has a historical heritage as follows:

1. Klungkung's role from the beginning was the center of the development of the kingdom on the island of Bali.
2. The role and function of the market that has existed since the time of the kingdom, its existence still exists and has developed until now. The trade center also developed to the main and surrounding roads with the development of a commercialization function
3. In the field of constitutional affairs, the office of the Regent of Klungkung, other regional government monuments, and offices, is established;
4. Conservation areas and relics of Klungkung buildings, namely, Klungkung castle, Kertha gosa, struggle monument, and gel-gel area

Figure 3. Historical building in the Klungkung urban area

Source: Author Analysis 2019

Art

In the arts field, Klungkung Subdistrict which has heterogeneous life due to cultural acculturation has developed several arts such as dance, kerawitan, literature, and fine art which are the identities of Klungkung urban area

Table 1. art in the Klungkung sub-district as a cultural space for urban areas

Dance	Karawitan	philology	art
Baris Jangkung	A ngklung	Pesantian	Anyaman
Baro ng	Baleganjur	Sastra Lisan	Atbai
Baro ng K et	G ambang		Cagcag
Baro ng N o ngkling	G end er W ayang		Gerbah
			Handicraft, gold, silver
Calo narang	Gong Kebyar		Metal / Iron Crafts
Gandrung	K lentangan		Sculpture Crafts
Genjek	Rebana		Peno k Crafts
Jauk	Saro n		

Sumrah, Qasidah, Pudat	Semar Pegulingan	Selongsong Peluru Crafts
Kebyar Duduk dance	Topeng	Uang Kepeng Crafts
Rejang dance		Pand e Besi
Telek		Endek weaving
Topeng Pajegan		Ikat weaving
Wayang Wong		Songket weaving

Source: cultural, youth and sports services of Klungkung District 2018

Values

The socio-cultural life of the people in Klungkung Subdistrict has its own characteristics because of the acculturation of culture between Balinese culture characterized by Hinduism and outside culture (non-Hindu). This cultural acculturation has been going on for a long time so that until now the life of Klungkung Urban is heterogeneous and continues well.

1. Community System.

Residents living in the Klungkung Subdistrict area are the majority of Balinese people who are Hindu who have cultural diversity, and the social system that is formed is according to prevailing customs such as pekurenan (family) and dadia (offspring) groups as a result of marriage. This is also characterized by the distribution of building elements or placement of Balinese cultural forms, such as temple buildings or holy places, banjar halls, and sacred areas such as the Great Crossroad

2. Customs

Communities in Klungkung Regency, especially in Mengwi Subdistrict, in interpreting the concepts of space are not very different from those in other areas of Bali. Tri hita karana philosophy contained in every legal rule or awig-awig traditional village is still manifested in the spatial concept in Klungkung Subdistrict, both macro, and micro.

Land use in the Klungkung urban area is divided into functions of the area with the main functions of natural, cultural and religious tourism, settlements, education and research, water tourism and village tourism, acting as tourist centers in the Klungkung area. With this role, the position of the Puri Klungkung tourist area, both in terms of regional development and equitable development, is an integral part of the development of the Klungkung urban area.

Fixed Cultural Space Settings

Shape of Building

The building orientation is more about traditional Balinese architecture, namely the existence of space based on the concept of sanga mandala and tri mandala. Whereas the orientation of trade buildings tends to face the road for the purpose of inviting buyers.

Open Space

Open space in the Klungkung urban area is the Klungkung town square, which can be used for various positive activities for the community and the local government. Public open space is a very important thing, which is an important element that can be a development and development of a closed urban area.

Semifixed Cultural Space Settings

Circulation and Parking

Circulation patterns and parking systems in the area generally use road bodies as are parking (on-street parking). Parking patterns like this greatly disrupt vehicle circulation, especially during busy hours. This parking pattern

can be seen along roads in urban areas, and there is no area that becomes a parking center that can accommodate orderliness and smooth circulation of vehicles

Pedestrian Area

The main pedestrian facilities are sidewalks located on the right and left the side of the arterial road, for the environment and local roads there are no walking facilities where pedestrians still use the road as a pedestrian lane. For in the core region, a total pedestrian facility needs to be developed where the speed of the vehicle will be diverted through other roads, so that the existence of a core and supporting area is closer and equally accessible to tourists.

Signage

Signage found in the region is only an area marker location element. Its character is still functional and does not have a design that characterizes regional identity. The dominant edge element is found in the planning area in the form of rivers, ponds, environmental guardrails, roadside, sidewalks, drainage channels, fences, gates, and marker lines road, in addition to differentiating the surface of the activity space is also a space limiting element such as the difference in the height of the road surface and the sidewalk. Another element that also acts as a space divider is tree element.

Nonfixed Cultural Space Setting

Activity Support

Support activities are all building functions and activities that support the public space of a city area. Supporters of activities in the Klungkung urban area are more trading businesses, street vendors, and services for both souvenir traders and food and beverage businesses. On the side of tourism, handicraft business and antic goods which are typical in Klungkung are Balinese kepeng money

Conservation

As the main area, Puri Klungkung is cultural tourism that should be preserved, both in terms of ritual activities and tourism activities. In this area, there is also a Bale Kambang named Kertha Gosa where the bale is located above the pool surrounding it. This means that the region is the most advanced, which will feel the impact of the increasing number of visitors. Gel-Gel Area. In this area, the main target of planning is the Merajan Agung Puri Gel-gel area and the Pura Dasar Bhuana area, which is a former area of Puri Gel-Gel.

Figure 4. the potential of cultural space as an identity of urban areas

Source: Author Analysis 2019

Table 2. Elements of cultural space as aspects forming the Urban Identity

Cultural Space Elements	Forming aspects of regional identity	Identity of the form of Urban area Development
Symbolic	History of tradition	Provide the main direction orientation to the center of urban areas
Functional	Values	Segmentation based on zones and functions of urban areas
Emotional	Trust	Harmony and harmonization of urban communities to gods, other communities and the surrounding environment
Culture	Art	The historical characteristics of the habits of the people from the past were maintained
Political	Kingdom / Castle	Policies and regulations from leaders to shape the character of urban areas
Spatial Settings	Elements fixed, semi-fixed, non-fixed	Provide space identities in each node in the urban area.

Source: Author Analysis 2019

CONCLUSION

1. The development of the Klungkung city area is seen from the history and space of the local culture. If viewed from its development since the establishment of the kingdom, resistance to colonialism, the transfer of the royal capital to the era of independence, the Klungkung region which is now the capital of samarapura has an important and very central role and has a historical heritage as follows: Bali. The role and function of the market that has existed since the kingdom era, its existence still exists and has developed until now. The trade center also developed into the main road and its surroundings with the development of a commercialization function. Conservation areas and relics of Klungkung buildings, namely, Puri Klungkung, Kertha gosa, struggle monuments, and gel area. In the development of increasingly rapid urban areas, a strategy is needed to build and develop cities while building their identities. It not only makes buildings to the regional level but creates conditions where there is harmony in each element. The most important thing to note is how to utilize the potential, architectural character, climate, and local culture that are used as the basis for planning and designing urban areas with identities.
2. There are several concepts of Bali Space Elements which are touches of identity for urban areas, namely the history of traditions and beliefs, a system of values, art and cultural, spatial planning that includes permanent, semi-permanent and non-permanent elements in development. With increasingly rapid urban areas, strategies and identities are needed to build and develop cities while building development ideas.
 - Symbolic elements of cultural space in the implementation of historical traditions Provide the main direction orientation to the center of urban areas
 - Elements of functional, cultural space in the implementation of value systems govern Segmentation based on zones and functions of urban areas
 - The emotional element of cultural space in applying trust provides harmony and harmonization of urban communities to deities, other communities, and the surrounding environment
 - Elements of cultural space in the implementation of art provide historical characteristics of people's habits from the past that are maintained
 - Establish cultural space elements in the implementation of fixed, semi-fix, and nonfiksation elements that provide space identity for each node in urban urban areas.

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